

«USE OF NEW PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN ENGLISH LESSONS»

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Abstract: This article will discuss the importance and effective methods of using new pedagogical technologies in English lessons in secondary schools.

Key words: pedagogical technology, pyramid of consciousness, skills, role-playing games.

The use of new pedagogical technologies in the system of continuous education. Non-traditional methods of teaching pedagogical technologies, in particular the interactive method, are widely introduced into the educational process. What is educational technology? Scientists, in particular, UNESCO specialists, have given different definitions to the concept of pedagogical technology, these definitions complement each other, revealing the essence of the concept. Pedagogical technology is a systematic method of identifying, creating and applying all the processes of learning and cognitive assimilation, taking into account technical features, human potential and their interaction in order to optimize the forms of education.

Pedagogical technologies - these processes consist of a set of means, methods that purposefully enhance the pedagogical impact on the formation of predetermined personal qualities in students. There are many guides on modern pedagogical teaching methods. In particular, "how many percent of the subject is described by the reader in memory, has it been mastered by him?". The end of the experiments in order to find the answer to this logical question was called the "Pyramid of Consciousness". Description of the item in his words:

- 10-20% of them only when they hear:
- 30-50% of students and teaching materials on the topic: if he hears, does practical exercises on the topic, tells and explains the topic to his friends, communicates with them from the surface of the topic, discusses, 60-90% of the topic will be remembered and learned. Therefore, it is of little use to the teacher to enter the classroom and lecture the student. The student should be able to communicate with his peers on the topic, participate in practical exercises, share knowledge gained in lectures. Then the knowledge gained will be solid. By

studying and comparing different styles and mindsets with peers, each teacher creates their own style.

Here are some non-traditional ways of learning: Independent work - after the completion of certain topics, the goal is to develop in students the skills of independent practical work, classes, textbooks, teaching aids. The teacher prepares the topic of independent work in advance. The sheet with the task can be issued to each student individually.

In English lessons, students work in pairs to communicate. Used to solve a problem. One student in a pair shares their thoughts on the task with a friend. She, in turn, explains to her first classmate that a couple of students take turns acting as a teacher.

Teach students to work in groups. The class is divided into groups. Each group can have 5-6 students. To make the grouping more objective, the teacher writes down the numbers 1-6 on paper of the same type. For example, if there are 36 students in a class, it is preferable to divide them into 6 groups. In this case, the teacher writes one number on 6 sheets, 2 numbers on 6 sheets, ..., 6 numbers on 6 sheets. The papers are shuffled and each student receives one paper.

Students with one number are assigned to the 1st group, and students to the 6th group. The task should be given to the groups clearly and concisely. Groups may differ on this issue. On behalf of each group, the student presents their group's ideas to the class. The teacher interprets, interprets and evaluates the activities of the groups. Working in groups, students learn to justify and express their ideas.

Role play: dramatization of a situation corresponding to the topic, acting out roles. The script should be structured in such a way that it helps the performers on stage acquire knowledge and skills. The teacher decides which topic is best to deliver. New pedagogical technologies are a key factor in the formation of activity and creative thinking of students. When conducting English lessons on the basis of new pedagogical technologies, both free thinking of students and the effectiveness of expressing the product of thought are formed. An integral part of the new technology of teaching a foreign language is the relationship between the student and the teacher with each other and with the educational material during the lesson.

“The concept of the new pedagogical technology, in short, is to make the student an active participant in the learning process. The student must learn,

work, explore and observe on his own, and the teacher must manage the complex process.

The mission of the general education school is to provide students with general information and educate them in the spirit of patriotism and national values. If students have pronunciation skills, especially the ability to distinguish sounds in a foreign language, and they have a certain stock of vocabulary and speech turns, they will understand it better when they hear a foreign language.

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